

ISic0093

I.Sicily inscription 0093

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Titiano · c(larissimo) · f(ilio) · C(ai) · Maesi(i)
2. Titiani · et · Fonteiae
3. Frontinae · consu
4. larium · filio
5. patricio · ob · hono
6. rem · togae · virilis
7. Clodius · Rufus · eques · romanus
8. amico · suo · incomparabili

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

To Titianus, the most illustrious son of Gaius Maesius Titianus and Fonteia Frontina (both) of consular rank, son of patrician birth. In honour (of his assumption) of the toga virilis. Clodius Rufus, a Roman knight, (made this) to his incomparable friend.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285284

EDR 127505

EDCS 22100047

Bibliography

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